

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6632496

THE IMPACT OF A BREAK DURING HEALTH-IMPROVING PHYSICAL CULTURE CLASSES CAUSED BY THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC ON THE SENSE OF TIME AMONG WOMEN

Ashot Chatinyan¹ – Professor, Doctor of pedagogical sciences.

Elena Hakobyan¹ – Professor, Doctor of pedagogical sciences;

[Email: elena.hakobyan@sportedu.am](mailto:elena.hakobyan@sportedu.am) .

¹Armenian state institute of physical culture and sport, Republic of Armenia;
Yerevan, Republic of Armenia, A. Manukyan 11Street.

ABSTRACT

The problem of evaluation and management of time intervals is relevant in all spheres of human activity, and especially in physical culture and sports. Knowledge on the features of time perception can help rationally organize various activities, maintain health and safety of human beings.

The aim of the research is to identify the features of the impact of a break in health improving physical education classes related to the coronavirus pandemic on the sense of time among elderly women.

Methods and organization of the research contain study and analysis of scientific and methodological literature, timekeeping, mathematical statistics. The study involved 21 women regularly engaged in physical culture in the health improving group at the Armenian State Institute of Physical Culture and Sport. The average age of women was 65.3 ± 2.49 years, engagement experience in the group was 15.57 ± 2.21 years on average.

Discussion of the research results. The 2019 coronavirus pandemic has had a negative impact on the health and safety of people's lives, as well as on all areas of human activity. There was a minor declination in the sense of evaluating short and long time period after one year break in health improving physical exercises. In particular, the indicators for 3 seconds decreased by an average of 0.04 seconds, whereas 10 seconds - by 0.15 seconds. Such minor declinations affected the unreliability of the difference between average indicators. We suggested that the health improving exercises developed across the lifespan and the implementation of various physical exercises with musical accompaniment contributed to the strong sense of time.

Conclusion. The results of years-long research confirm that engagement in health improving physical exercises on a regular basis has a positive effect on enabling women to accurately feel a short and long period of time. It is worth noting that a one-year break in classes did not worsen the indicators studied. Meanwhile, it was revealed that women more accurately assess a short time interval (3 s).

Key words: women, health improving physical culture, sense of time.

Introduction. Every person daily faces the problem of time, since time is an important regulator of his activity. The perception of time plays a pivotal role in helping people get oriented in the world around them and adapted in various situations related to professional activities, everyday life and recreation. There are many specialties in which one can succeed due to the accurate perception of time. Thus, for example, in the system of interaction between man and car in a wide range of activities, the life and well-being of other people depend on the orientation in

time. In this regard an important question is the extent to which the driver demonstrates accuracy and speed of reactions and the operator produces numerous processes in case of complicated and sudden situations.

The problem of assessment and management of time intervals is a relevant focus area for physical culture and sport. Knowledge on the features of time perception can help rationally organize various activities, maintain health and safety of human beings. According to researches carried out by D.G. Elkin back in the 70s of the last century, a positive relationship was established between the perception of time and the effectiveness of activities. The revealed relationship indicates that the more accurate the perception of time, the more successful the human activity is [5].

However, the issue linked to the age impact on the perception of diverse time periods and dynamics of various manifestations of movement accuracy is understudied to day and presents scientific and applied interest for specialists in the field of physical culture and sport.

In another study, conducted on a contingent of people involved in oriental types of health improving physical culture (qigong, wushu and tai chi quan), the influence of various psychomotor abilities on the coherence of controlling the spatio-temporal parameters of procedural and final accuracy in movements with a complex motor structure was studied [2]. As the author notes, the correlation pattern of the studied indicators among representatives of oriental health systems has some features in the structural and content components. At the same time, it was disclosed the influence of classes under the eastern system on the ability to coordinate and control movements of various coordination complexity. The author states that a high level of development of the ability to control internal efforts, the ability to concentrate attention and control the flow of energy and consciousness, which are characteristic of Eastern health systems, directly affect the level of psychomotor manifestation and the accuracy of spatio-temporal parameters of movements.

To this end, it should be noted that we have previously studied the age-related aspects of indicators dynamics related to the accuracy of time intervals management among women involved in health improving physical culture [3].

With regret, we have to underline the insufficiency of studying the issue linked to movement accuracy, changes in various motor abilities of mature and elderly people. Their optimal level of life is important for maintaining health, ensuring comfortable living and safety.

The aim of the research is to identify the features of the impact of a break in health improving physical education classes related to the coronavirus pandemic on the sense of time among elderly women.

Methods and organization of the research contain study and analysis of scientific and methodological literature, timekeeping, mathematical statistics.

The ability of women to evaluate time intervals was studied in short (3 s.) and long (10 s.) segments. The criterion for the accuracy of its assessment was the magnitude of the difference between the task and the average results shown in three attempts. The smaller the difference (error), the more accurately the person under test estimated a specific time interval. The task was completed without visual control by independently switching on and off the electronic stopwatch.

In order to study the impact of a break during long-term health improving physical education classes associated with the coronavirus pandemic on the ability of women to manage the temporal parameters of movements, a study was organized in which 21 women regularly engaged in physical education in the health improving group at the Armenian State Institute of

Physical Culture and Sport took part. The average age of women was 65.3 ± 2.49 years, engagement experience in the group was 15.57 ± 2.21 years on average.

The study was organized in stages: the 1st stage - in November 2019 and the 2nd - in March 2021, immediately after the lifting of restrictions related to the COVID pandemic and the resumption of classes in the health improving group.

Discussion of the research results.

Previously conducted panel studies were aimed at revealing the effect of long-term health improving physical culture on the ability of women to evaluate time intervals [4]. The age-related aspects of indicators dynamics related to the accuracy of time intervals management among women

An analysis of the dynamics of accuracy indicators for assessing a short (3 s) time interval showed that in the first group of women (45-55 years old) there is a minor improvement in the ability to manage a 3-second interval. For eight years of training, the error while performing the control task decreased by 0.13 s. (Table 1). In the second age group (56-65 years and older), the studied indicator declined by an average of 0.05 s. It should be noted that in both cases the changes were not significant.

Table 1

The dynamics of accuracy indicators for estimating time intervals among women throughout an eight-year panel study (errors)

Stages Researches (year)	Timeslot estimation accuracy					
	Duration					
	3 s.			10 s.		
	X±m	t	P	X±m	t	P
	1st group (n=11)					
2011	0,58±0,09	---	---	0,99±0,19	---	---
2019	0,45±0,07	1,18	<0,05	0,96±0,14	0,13	<0,05
2 nd group (n= 9)						
2011	0,68±0,12	---	---	2,81±0,46	---	---
2019	0,73±0,14	0,28	<0,05	2,48±0,29	0,61	<0,05

With regard to the accuracy of estimating a long-time interval (10 s), somewhat different data were obtained. It turned out that the ability of women to evaluate this time interval in the first age group remained virtually unchanged. At the end of the eight-year period of training in the health improving group, the error increased by only 0.03s. In the older age group of women, panel studies revealed some (0.33 s) improvement in the ability to differentiate 10 s. time interval ($P \geq 0.05$).

This kind of change in parameters under the study indicates that, despite the older age and accordingly the greater experience in performing various motor actions related to the assessment and regulation of time intervals, managing a long-time interval is a more complex ability than managing a short interval. Apparently, the age factor and the resulting involuntional processes in the CNS affect primarily the perception of long (10 s) time intervals.

The 2019 coronavirus pandemic has had a negative impact on the health and safety of people's lives, as well as on all areas of human activity. Its influence negatively affected both sport related activities and different forms of organizing physical education for all age groups of the

population. In this aspect, it was interesting to identify the effect of a break in classes during the pandemic on the sense of time among women involved in health improving physical culture for many years (Table 2).

Table2

Dynamics of indicators of different time intervals perception among women due to a break in health improving physical culture classes caused by the Coronavirus Pandemic ($X \pm m$), (n=21)

№	Stages Researches (year)	Duration (s)		Validity of differences	
		3	10	t	P
1.	2019	0,46±0,04	1,03±0,14	4,07	≤ 0,001
2.	2021	0,5±0,08	1,28±0,14	4,88	≤ 0,001
3.	t	0,44	0,75	----	----
4.	P	≥ 0,05	≥ 0,05	----	----

Foremost, we were curious to see the change in the studied indicators associated with the termination of classes in the health improving group due to restrictions caused by the coronavirus. It turned out to be a minor declination in the sense of evaluating short and long time period after one year break in health improving physical exercises. In particular, the indicators for 3 seconds worsened by an average of 0.04 seconds, and 10 seconds - by 0.15 seconds. Such minor declinations affected the unreliability of the difference between average indicators. We suggested that the health improving exercises developed across the lifespan and the implementation of various physical exercises with musical accompaniment contributed to the strong sense of time. At the same time, when calculating the accuracy per unit of time, it turned out that women, while assessing a short and long-time interval, were mistaken by almost the same value: 0.15 and 0.1 seconds, respectively. Based on the analysis of scientific literature conducted by Yu.V. Koryagina, some researchers believe that "there is not one, but several mechanisms in the body which provide a reflection of temporal parameters." Obviously this is due to various relations between the processes of time reflection and the characteristics of physiological functions within various body structures [1].

For comparison, we call for the results of one of the studies which shows the errors of 20 older women while assessing a 10-second time interval corresponding to almost 5 seconds. It is noteworthy that retesting this ability a year later showed a declination in the accuracy of estimating the time interval by almost 2 seconds. Younger people more accurately estimated this period of time [6].

Comparative analysis of indicators for evaluating short and long-time intervals demonstrate that a short time period is estimated almost twice as accurately. It is remarkable that the identified difference in time estimation occurred both in the 2019 studies and two years after the resumption of classes. In particular, if prior to the coronavirus pandemic, the difference in the assessment of a short and long-time interval was 0.57, then in 2021 it increased by 0.2 units and amounted to 0.78 seconds. The increase in difference was driven by an overall declination in women's ability to evaluate both short and long-time intervals by 0.04 and 0.25 seconds.

Conclusion. The results of years-long research confirm that engagement in health improving physical exercises on a regular basis has a positive effect on enabling women to accurately feel a short and long period of time. It is worth noting that a one-year break in classes did not worsen the indicators studied. Meanwhile, it was revealed that women more accurately assess a short time interval (3 s).

References

1. Koryagina Yu.V. Perception of time and space in sport activities. - M.: Scientific Publisher "Theory and Practice of Physical Culture and Sports 2006. - 224 p.
2. Liu Yun Qian. Mutual influence of psychomotor and spatio-temporal parameters on the efficiency of motor actions engaged in oriental types of health-improving physical culture // Pedagogy, psychology and medical and biological problems of physical development in sport. - 2014. - No. 6 - P. 26-30.
3. Chatinyan A.A., Akopyan E.S. Features of the age based dynamics of time management indicators in women. Materials of the international scientific congress "Sport. Olympism, Health". Volume II, Chisinau, 2016. - P. 622-627.
4. Chatinyan A.A., Akopyan E.S. Influence of the consequences of the coronavirus pandemic on the control of movements in women involved in health-improving physical culture: panel studies. Science and sport: current trends. - 2021. - V. 9, No. 4. - P. 107-113.
5. Elkin, D.G. Perception of time / D.G. Elkin. - M.: Publisher of the APN RSFSR, 1962. - 312 p.
6. Jonathan W. Anderson, Alicia D. Rueda, M. Schmitter - Edgecombe. The Stability of Time Estimation in Older Adults // Int'l. J. Aging and human development. -2014, vol. 78(3), pp. 259-276.